

THE EFFECT OF *Vernonia amygdalina* Del. (BITTER LEAF) LEAF EXTRACT ON THE LIPID PROFILE OF WISTAR ALBINO RATS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of aqueous leaf extract of *Vernonia amygdalina* Del. (bitter leaf) on the lipid profile of Wistar rats. The rats were divided into 3 groups. Control group were given no leaf extract, low dose group were given 0.5ml of leaf extract and high dose group given 1ml of the extract. Animals given 1ml of extract had a highly significant decrease of Total-Chol, LDL-Chol and Triglycerides concentrations with mean and standard deviation of 112.89 ± 1.08 , 69.71 ± 2.32 and 96.21 ± 0.71 (mg/dl) respectively compared with control group with mean and standard deviation of 199.89 ± 1.42 , 74.50 ± 1.93 and 105.11 ± 2.36 (mg/dl) respectively. Low dose animal also showed a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) of 116.34 ± 1.38 , 71.77 ± 2.27 and 100.86 ± 1.06 respectively compared with control group. High dose animals showed no significant change in HDL-Cholesterol concentration (23.93 ± 0.71) compared with control group (24.36 ± 0.83) at ($P < 0.05$), likewise low dose group (24.40 ± 1.01). The result reveals that *V. amygdalina* causes a significant reduction in the lipid profile ($P < 0.05$) especially Total-Chol, LDL-Chol and Triglycerides. It also produced significant change in body weight after 21 days. The study therefore confirms that bitter leaf (*V. amygdalina*) has hypolipidaemic properties.

KEYWORDS: Wistar rats, *Vernonia amygdalina*, leaf extract, lipid profile, Triglycerides

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INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have formed the basis of health care throughout the world since the earlier days of humanity and are still widely used and have considerable importance in international trade (Ahmed, 2010). In certain African countries for instance, up to 90% of the population still rely exclusively on plants as a source of medicine (Hostettmann, 2011). As a consequence, the World Health Organization (WHO) had in one of its charter in Geneva recommended further investigation into this area, particularly as it concerns chronic and debilitating diseases such as diabetes mellitus.

Many people in Nigeria are now becoming increasingly interested in harnessing the nature provided herbs as regards to orthodox medicine. Many problems like diabetes, malaria, high blood pressure, dysentery, worm infestation, cancer, diarrhea and many diseases have been handled traditionally with these medicinal plants (Akah and Okafor, 2008).

The people of Nigeria have been using the leaves of *Vernonia amygdalina* popularly known as bitter leaf. It belongs to the plant family Asteraceae or Compositae, and the genus *Vernonia*. *Vernonia* is a genus of about 1000 species of forbs and shrubs in the family Asteraceae. Some species are edible and of economic value. They

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are known for having intense purple flowers. The genus was named by an English botanist *William Vernon* (Keay, 2009). This has led some botanists to divide this large genus into smaller groups which separate the species into distinct genera. Several species of *Vernonia*, including; *V. calvoana*, *V. amygdalina* and *V. colorata* are eaten as leaf vegetables. *V. amygdalina* is a bushy shrub or well-formed tree up to 7m in height with petiolate leaf of about 6mm diameter and elliptical shape. The bark is rusty to dark-brown. The leaves are green with a characteristic color and bitter taste (Ijeh, *et al*: 1996). Leaves are lanceolate to oblong; up to 28x10cm, but usually about 10-15 x 4-5cm, leathery, medium to dark green, with or without sparse hairs above, with fine soft, pale hairs below and conspicuous reticulate veins; apex are tapering, base always almost symmetrical, margin entire or very finely toothed; petiole usually very short but may be 1-2cm long. Flower heads is thistlelike, small, creamy white, sometimes slightly touched with mauve, about 10mm long, grouped in dense heads, axillary and terminal, forming large flat clusters about 15cm in diameter but not conspicuous; sweetly scented, especially in the evening. Fruit is a small nutlet, with minute glands and bristly hairs on the body and a long tuft of bristly hairs at the top. It is used in Nigeria for both therapeutic and nutritional purposes.

Lipids are chemically diversified group of organic materials of biological origin. It includes all fats and substance of a fat-like nature. Lipids are practically insoluble in water but readily soluble in organic nonpolar (chloroform, diethylene, benzene, dichloroethyl, etc) solvent. They are utilizable in metabolism by living organisms (Nwanjo, 2004).

The principal forms of lipids found in the human plasma include fatty acids, triacylglycerol, cholesterol and phospholipids. There are other physiological important lipid-soluble substances like vitamin A, D and K. However, the lipids of major physiological significance are fatty acids, triacylglycerol, phospholipids and cholesterol (Nduka, 1999).

This work was carried out to test the potentiality of this widely used plant in reducing the level of plasma lipids; to know the least concentration at which the plant extract can be effective in reducing the level of plasma lipids, and to know the least concentration at which the plant extract can influence the atherogenic risk predictor indices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fresh, mature, green leaves of *Vernonia amygdalina* was harvested from a natural habitat in Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria in July 2013. The botanical identification of the plant leaf was confirmed by Mercy Ajuru, (Plant Taxonomist, Department of Biology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt).The voucher specimens are kept in the University Herbarium for reference purpose.

METHODS:

PROCESSING OF LEAVES:

Fresh leaves of *V. amygdalina* were first sorted to remove dry ones. They were washed gently without squeezing to remove dirt and debris, and then sun dried for two weeks. The dried leaves were ground into powder in Mile 3 market Mill. The powder was sieved through a 1mm sieve to get a fine powder. The coarse powder was discarded. The fine powder was used for the extraction.

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE

One hundred and fifty grams (150g) of the powder was put in 1 litre beaker and then water added to make up 800mls. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and left to stand for 24 hours at room temperature. It was then filtered using a filter paper. The filtrate was then placed in a bottle and labeled *Vernonia amygdalina* leaf solution and then stored in a refrigerator at 4°C.

ADMINISTRATION OF EXTRACT

The extraction was given orally and the animals were forced to drink the extraction by compulsion. The rats were divided into 3 groups of 6 rats in each group. They were housed separately in plastic and stainless steel cages labeled group 1, 2, and 3. The rats in group 1 were administered 1ml of the extract. Group 2 were given

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0.5ml of the extract and group 3 was taken as the control group and no leaf extract was given to them. The weight of each animal was taken before commencement of experiment.

ANIMALS

Eighteen (18) adult rats (males) of Wistar strain weighing 200-250g were carefully selected and used in the experiment. The rats were purchased at the Department of Pharmaceutical Science, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Rivers State, and transported in a ventilated carton in a bus to the animal house located at Seat of Wisdom Chaplaincy, Catholic Church, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt.

The animals were fed with commercially prepared chicken powder's mash for 10 days to allow them to acclimatize with the laboratory conditions.

MEASUREMENT OF BODY WEIGHT

The weights of the animals were obtained using a weighing balance (Salter, Model 250). Each of the animals were placed carefully on the stainless tray of the weighing balance and allowed to remain calm before the readings were taken from the pointer of the instrument. The reading obtained from each animal was recorded. Animals were weighed on the first day and the last day of the experiment. The weight gain/loss was obtained by subtracting the weight on the first day (initial body weight).

BLOOD COLLECTION

Twelve hours after last feeding and treatment (overnight fasting), the rats in all the groups were sacrificed. Using a sterile syringe and needle, whole blood was obtained through cardiac puncture and put into a plain tube. It was allowed for 30 minutes to clot and transferred into a centrifuge tube. The blood was then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3,000rpm to facilitate separation, remove cells and recover serum used for biochemical assays. (Using Wisperfuge 1384 centrifuge Tamson, Holland). The supernatant after centrifugation, which is the serum, was used for different lipoprotein assays. This was done on each blood sample collected from each rat in the different groups (1, 2 and 3).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Numerical variables are reported as Mean $\pm$ SD. Case-control comparison was performed using students' t-test. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered significant

RESULTS

Table 1 Mean $\pm$ Standard deviation of analyzed lipid profile of control, low dose and high dose treated animals respectively

PARAMETERS	LIPID PROFILE				
	T-CHOL	TRIGS	HDL	LDL	
VLDL					
(mg/dl)					
CONTROL (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	199.89 $\pm$ 1.42	105.11 $\pm$ 2.36	24.36 $\pm$ 0.83	74.50 $\pm$ 1.93	21.02 $\pm$ 0.47
LOW DOSE (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	116.34 $\pm$ 1.38	100.86 $\pm$ 1.06	24.40 $\pm$ 1.01	71.77 $\pm$ 2.27	20.17 $\pm$ 0.21
HIGH DOSE (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	112.89 $\pm$ 1.08	96.21 $\pm$ 0.71	23.93 $\pm$ 0.71	69.71 $\pm$ 2.32	19.24 $\pm$ 0.30

T-CHOL=Total cholesterol

TRIGS = Triglycerides

VLDL = Very low density lipoprotein

HDL= High density lipoprotein

LDL = Low density lipoprotein

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Significantly different when compared with control ($p < 0.05$).

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Table 1 depicts the mean and standard deviation of the lipid profile for the control, low dose and high dose. The control group has the following values for Total cholesterol 199.89 ± 1.42 , Triglycerides 105.11 ± 2.36 , High density lipoprotein (HDL) 24.36 ± 0.83 , Low density lipoprotein (LDL) 74.50 ± 1.93 and Very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) 21.02 ± 0.47 respectively. Low dose group has the following values for Total cholesterol 116.34 ± 1.38 , Triglycerides 100.86 ± 1.06 , High density lipoprotein (HDL) 24.40 ± 1.01 , Low density lipoprotein (LDL) 71.77 ± 2.27 and Very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) 20.17 ± 0.21 respectively. High dose group has the following values for Total cholesterol 112.89 ± 1.08 , Triglycerides 96.21 ± 0.71 , High density lipoprotein (HDL) 23.93 ± 0.71 , Low density lipoprotein (LDL) 69.71 ± 2.32 and Very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) 19.24 ± 0.30 respectively.

Table 2 T-test comparison of control group and low dose group showing the level of significance among the parameters.

	ANALYTES/ TESTS in mg/dl				
	T-CHOL	TRIGS.	HDL	LDL	VLDL
CONTROL					
(MEAN $\pm$ SD)	199.89 ± 2.36	105.11 ± 2.36	24.36 ± 0.83	74.50 ± 1.93	21.02 ± 0.47
LOW DOSE					
(MEAN $\pm$ SD)	116.34 ± 1.38	100.86 ± 1.06	24.40 ± 1.01	71.77 ± 2.27	20.17 ± 0.21
T-statistics	3.99	3.66	-0.05	2.04	3.66
At $P < 0.05$	S	S	NS	S	S

T-critical = 1.81

NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT

S = SIGNIFICANT

SD =Standard Deviation

Table 2 shows the comparison between Control group and Low dose group lipid profile in mg/dl, the considered parameters are T-chol, TRIGS, HDL, LDL and VLDL. There was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the T-chol in both groups since T-statistics ($3.99 > T$ critical). The TRIGS, LDL and VLDL of the test also recorded significant differences (decrease) in lipid profile of Low dose group since their T statistics ($3.66, 2.04$ and 3.66 respectively) $> T$ critical ($P < 0.05$). There was significant difference (increase) on HDL as T statistic $< T$ critical.

Table 3 T-test comparison of control group and High dose group showing the level of significance among the parameters.

	ANALYTES/ TESTS in mg/dl				
	T-CHOL	TRIGS.	HDL	LDL	VLDL
CONTROL					
(MEAN $\pm$ SD)	199.89 ± 2.36	105.11 ± 2.36	24.36 ± 0.83	74.50 ± 1.93	21.02 ± 0.47
HIGH DOSE					
(MEAN $\pm$ SD)	112.89 ± 1.08	96.21 ± 0.71	23.93 ± 0.71	69.71 ± 2.32	19.24 ± 0.30
T-statistics	6.19	7.08	0.86	3.54	7.08
At $P < 0.05$	S	S	NS	S	S

T-critical = 1.81

NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT

S = SIGNIFICANT

SD =Standard Deviation

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Table 3 shows the comparison between Control group and Low dose group lipid profile in mg/dl, the considered parameters are T-chol, TRIGS, HDL, LDL and VLDL. There was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the TRIGS in both groups since T-statistics (7.08) > T critical. The T-chol, LDL and VLDL of the test also recorded significant differences (decrease) in lipid profile of high dose group since their T statistics (6.19, 3.54 and 7.08 respectively) > T critical ($P < 0.05$). There was significant difference (increase) on HDL as T statistic < T critical.

Table 4 T-test comparison of Low dose group and High dose group showing the level of significance among the parameters.

	ANALYTES/ TESTS in mg/dl				
	T-CHOL	TRIGS.	HDL	LDL	VLDL
LOW DOSE (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	116.34 $\pm$ 1.38	100.86 $\pm$ 1.06	24.40 $\pm$ 1.01	71.77 $\pm$ 2.27	20.17 $\pm$ 0.21
HIGH DOSE (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	112.89 $\pm$ 1.08	96.21 $\pm$ 0.71	23.93 $\pm$ 0.71	69.71 $\pm$ 2.32	19.24 $\pm$ 0.30
T-statistics	3.08	5.58	0.83	2.88	5.58
At $P < 0.05$	S	S	NS	S	S

T-critical = 1.81

NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT

S = SIGNIFICANT

SD = Standard Deviation

Table 4 shows the comparison between Low dose group and High dose group lipid profile in mg/dl, the considered parameters are T-chol, TRIGS, HDL, LDL and VLDL. There was significant difference (decrease) ($P < 0.05$) in the LDL in both groups since T-statistics (2.88) > T critical. The T-chol, TRIGS and VLDL of the test also recorded significant differences (decrease) in lipid profile of high dose group since their T statistics (3.08, 5.58 and 5.58 respectively) > T critical ($P < 0.05$). There was significant difference (increase) on HDL as T statistic < T critical.

Table 5 Mean $\pm$ Standard deviation of initial and final body weight of control, low dose and high dose groups respectively.

	BODY WEIGHT (gm)		
	CONTROL	LOW DOSE	HIGH DOSE
INITIAL BODY WEIGHT (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	223.33 $\pm$ 18.85	228.33 $\pm$ 19.50	226.66 $\pm$ 19.93
FINAL BODY WEIGHT (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	234.16 $\pm$ 17.89	220.83 $\pm$ 19.45	212.50 $\pm$ 19.31

Table 5 depicts the mean and standard deviation of initial body body weight and final body weight for the control, low dose and high dose groups. The initial body weight has the following values for Control group 199.89 $\pm$ 1.42, Low dose group 105.11 $\pm$ 2.36 and High dose group 24.36 $\pm$ 0.83 respectively. The final body weight has the following values for Control group 116.34 $\pm$ 1.38, Low dose group 100.86 $\pm$ 1.06 and High dose group 24.40 $\pm$ 1.01 respectively.

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Table 6 T-test comparison of Initial body weight in Control group and Final body weight in Control group showing the level of significance among the parameters.

BODY WEIGHT (gm)			
	INITIAL BODY WEIGHT	FINAL BODY WEIGHT	T- statistics
CONTROL (MEAN ± SD) At P< 0.05	223.33 ± 18.85	234.16 ± 17.89	- 0.93 NS

T-critical = 1.81

NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT

SD =Standard Deviation

Table 6 shows the comparison of Initial body weight in Control group and Final body weight in Control group all in gm, the considered parameter is change in body weight. There was no significant difference (P<0.05) in both groups since T-statistics (-0.93) < T critical.

Table 7 T-test comparison of Initial body weight in Low dose group and Final body weight in Low dose group showing the level of significance among the parameters.

BODY WEIGHT (gm)			
	INITIAL BODY WEIGHT	FINAL BODY WEIGHT	T- statistics
LOW DOSE (MEAN ± SD) At P< 0.05	228.33 ± 19.50	220.83 ± 19.45	0.60 NS

T-critical = 1.81

NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT

SD =Standard Deviation

Table 7 shows the comparison of Initial body weight in Low dose group and Final body weight in Low dose group all in gm, the considered parameter is change in body weight. There was no significant difference (P<0.05) in both groups since T-statistics (0.60) < T critical.

Table 8 T-test comparison of Initial body weight in High dose group and Final body weight in High dose group showing the level of significance among the parameters.

BODY WEIGHT (gm)			
	INITIAL BODY WEIGHT	FINAL BODY WEIGHT	T- statistics
HIGH DOSE (MEAN ± SD) At P< 0.05	226.66 ± 19.93	212.50 ± 19.31	1.14 NS

T-critical = 1.81

NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT

SD =Standard Deviation

Table 8 shows the comparison of Initial body weight in High dose group and Final body weight in High dose group all in gm, the considered parameter is change in body weight. There was no significant difference (P<0.05) in both groups since T-statistics (1.14) < T critical.

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DISCUSSION

The result of this study clearly indicates that oral administration of aqueous leaf extract of *V. amygdalina* produced hypolipidaemic effect. The result is consistent with earlier reports of Akah and Okafor (2008), Nwanjo, (2005) and Omoruyi, *et al.*, (1996) on the hypolipidaemic and antioxidative action of extract of *V. amygdalina* in Wister albino rats. Furthermore, the data obtained after 21 days treatment with the aqueous extract of *V. amygdalina* showed that the animals' weight decreased.

Past studies carried out by Defronzo and Ferrannijmi (1991), have shown that insulin sensitivity in the body improves with weight loss, and possibly because of an improvement in insulin stimulated reduction in the lipoprotein lipase (LPL) activity, thus producing low lipid content in the adipose tissues and resultant body weight loss.

The data obtained shows that serum LDL-Cholesterol concentration of animals treated with both 0.5ml and 1.0ml aqueous leaf extract of *V. amygdalina* decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) when compared with the control group. The high levels of antioxidants found in *V. amygdalina* conferred an improvement in antioxidant status as noted by increased oxidation of LDL (Deirdre and Frank, 2009). The results of the present study clearly demonstrate that aqueous leaf extract of *V. amygdalina* significantly has a hypolipidaemic effect. This depends on the nature and concentration of the extract. Future studies are required to identify compound(s) in aqueous leaf extract of *V. amygdalina* responsible for the hypolipidaemic effect.

The result shows some significant lowering effect on serum LDL-Cholesterol concentration from 76mg/dl of control to 69.14mg/dl and 69.27mg/dl in low dose and high dose treated animals respectively as against HDL-Cholesterol that was significantly increased by the treatment. Increased levels of HDL may be attributed to the relative polyunsaturated fatty acid composition of the *V. amygdalina* (Mensik, *et al.*, 2003) Triglyceride and VLDL-Cholesterol concentrations were also significantly reduced. This was not in conformity with the report of Arit *et al.*, (2007) that extract of *V. amygdalina* did not affect lipid profile significantly.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, the evidence summarized in this review indicate that there are significant changes on the lipid profiles of the test group when compared to the control group and that *V. amygdalina* can be incorporated into one's diet as it is safe for consumption, since the use of the plant will not likely contribute to any disease associated with hyperlipidaemia.

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